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Assessing knowledge and implementation gaps in soil health: an analysis from stakeholders

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Despite the European Union establishing an ambitious legislative framework—including the recent Soil Monitoring Law—and making significant scientific progress in understanding soil health, 60%–70% of EU soils remain unhealthy. This persistence of degradation highlights a potential disconnect between policy ambition and reality. This study—conducted within the EU “Benchmarks” project - investigates whether specific knowledge gaps are hindering the implementation of sustainable soil management (SSM) and the delivery of ecosystem services. We conducted a quantitative stakeholder perception analysis using a structured questionnaire based on the 13 action areas of the EU Soil Strategy for 2030. Data were collected from 79 experts across various sectors (Research, Government, NGOs, Education) using a purposive sampling strategy to identify soil knowledge gaps and prioritize intervention points based on the perceived urgency of knowledge and implementation failures. The analysis reveals a “Governance-Science Gap”. While stakeholders report high confidence in technical monitoring tools (e.g., LUCAS, Copernicus), they identify critical failures in integrating ecosystem services into political decision-making, defining actionable SSM practices and securing adequate funding. Disaggregated data show distinct perceptual disconnects; NGOs prioritize practical actions and funding, whereas researchers focus on theoretical gaps in climate and biodiversity. Comparing these findings with other EU initiatives (Soil Mission Support (SMS) and SOLO projects), we conclude that the primary barrier to soil health is not a lack of fundamental data, but a “Technical-Institutional Mismatch”. Future Research and Innovation (R&I) must therefore shift focus from data generation (Knowledge Development Gaps) to governance (e.g. research in developing approaches and tools to support informed decision), economic incentives, and educational frameworks (Knowledge Gaps) to translate science into effective stewardship. These exploratory findings warrant confirmation through larger-scale surveys but offer an evidence-based, stakeholder-driven diagnosis of priority areas for EU soil policy implementation.

KEYWORDS

EU soil policy, governance-science gap, knowledge-action gap, policy implementation, soil health, stakeholder perception, sustainable soil management

1 Introduction

The European Union has established an ambitious framework for the protection, sustainable management, and restoration of soils, recognizing soil health as foundational to climate change mitigation, biodiversity preservation, food security, and water quality.

In recent years, the EU has produced several binding policy documents directly or indirectly connected to soils and soil health. Among these are: (i) the recently adopted Soil Monitoring and Resilience Law (Directive (EU) 2025/2360) (European Commission, 2025); (ii) the Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2023/839); (iii) the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (Regulation (EU) 2024/3012) (European Commission, 2024c); and (iv) the Nature Restoration Law (Regulation (EU) 2024/1991) (European Commission, 2024b). In addition to these binding instruments, strategic legal documents have been introduced, such as (v) the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (COM 2020/380 final) (European Commission, 2020a); (vi) the Farm to Fork Strategy (COM 2020/381) (European Commission, 2020b); and (vii) the EU Soil Strategy for 2030 (COM 2021/699) (European Commission, 2021a; European Commission, 2021b).

Parallel to these policy efforts, significant scientific advancements have been made regarding the sustainable use of soils, including developments in Earth Observation (EO), the Internet of Things (IoT), and digital soil mapping (an overview on this subject is provided by Terribile et al. (2024); McBratney et al. (2025)).

Despite the ambitious legislative architecture cited above and the significant progress in soil science (Sellami et al., 2025), it is evident that the biophysical reality of European soils remains critical. For instance, recent assessments by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) and the European Environment Agency (EEA) indicate that between 60% and 70% of soils in the EU are currently in an unhealthy condition (JRC & EEA, 2024; European Commission, 2024a). This degradation is driven by a convergence of pressures: water erosion currently impacts approximately 24% of EU lands, resulting in an estimated loss of 1 billion tonnes of soil annually (Panagos et al., 2024). Furthermore, nutrient imbalances—specifically nitrogen surpluses—affect 74% of agricultural land, while soil organic carbon stocks in croplands are declining at a rate that undermines the EU's climate neutrality targets (JRC & EEA, 2024).

The persistence of these stressors highlights a significant gap between policy ambition and on-the-ground reality. Beyond the ecological implications, current rates of soil degradation impose a severe economic burden, with conservative estimates placing the cost of soil inaction between €50 billion and €72 billion per year (Panagos et al., 2024; European Commission, 2023). Consequently, while legal mechanisms for protection are now in place, the functional recovery of European soil systems has yet to be realized. Unfortunately, this evidence parallels recent findings from recent SDG reporting (UN, 2025), which indicate that the world is largely off track; only 35% of SDG targets show adequate progress, while nearly half are advancing too slowly and 18% have regressed compared to 2015 levels. This negative trend is particularly acute regarding Goal 15 (Life on Land), where soil degradation has intensified, with the proportion of degraded land rising from 11.3% in 2015 to 15.5% in 2019.

Understanding why ambitious policy frameworks fail to deliver on-the-ground results requires looking beyond biophysical monitoring data to examine the perceptions of those responsible

for implementing, researching, and advocating for soil health. Stakeholder perception analyses are increasingly recognized as essential complements to empirical assessments in environmental governance, as they reveal where institutional, cognitive, and practical barriers impede the translation of knowledge into action (Díaz et al., 2018; Stevance et al., 2019). Such analyses are particularly valuable for identifying mismatches between what science produces and what policy and practice actually need—the so-called “knowledge-action gap” (Löbmann et al., 2022). While biophysical data tells us what is happening to soils, stakeholder perceptions tell us where and why the system is failing to translate knowledge into effective stewardship.

While previous studies have documented the extent of soil degradation and while substantial bibliometric and expert-led analyses of soil knowledge gaps have been conducted (Mason et al., 2023; Roca Vallejo et al., 2025), there is very limited systematic, policy-aligned quantification of where knowledge gaps are most acutely perceived by a broad range of stakeholders (e.g. Pulido et al., 2024; Section 4.4 of this paper). This study addresses this gap. We aim to quantify knowledge and implementation gaps using data collected through a questionnaire distributed to a wide variety of expert stakeholders engaged in soil health issues. The objective was to enable key soil actors to prioritize intervention points based on the perceived urgency (on a scale of 1–5) of resolving knowledge gaps and implementation failures.

In designing the questionnaire, we moved away from a purely academic viewpoint and instead focused on active policy documents as the foundation for our inquiry. We designed our questionnaire using the EU Soil Strategy for 2030 (COM 2021/699 final), which outlines 13 critical key areas. The findings obtained from the analysis of the questionnaires were then compared with similar work produced within the EU by other scholars to triangulate our conclusions.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Survey design and policy alignment

The questionnaire was designed to allow a wide range of expert stakeholders to evaluate the existence and extent of knowledge gaps regarding soil health. To develop this questionnaire, we required a relevant benchmark. Rather than using frameworks produced by scientists, we sought out soil policy documents that provided comprehensive coverage of soil challenges, including their interdisciplinary aspects. Among the many documents available, we chose the Soil Strategy for 2030 (COM 2021/699) due to its comprehensive coverage of the EU policy agenda. Furthermore, the document remains relevant to the recently approved Soil Monitoring Law (Directive (EU) 2025/2360) and other important EU policies (e.g., CAP, Water Framework Directive, Nitrates Directive).

The questionnaire was divided into 14 sections: the first aimed to identify stakeholder characteristics, while the remaining 13 corresponded to the topics highlighted in the Soil Strategy for 2030 (Table 1).

The 64 rating questions (see Supplementary Material, Annex I) were derived through a systematic mapping exercise. The research team extracted each discrete action or objective articulated within the 13 thematic areas of the Soil Strategy, yielding an initial pool of

TABLE 1 The 13 sections outlined in the questionnaire provided to stakeholders.

Section number	Section topic
1	Soil for climate change mitigation and Adaptation
2	Soil and the circular economy
3	Soil biodiversity for human, animal and plant health
4	Soil for healthy water resources
5	Making sustainable soil management (SSM) the new normal
6	Preventing desertification
7	Preventing soil pollution
8	Restoring degraded soils and remediating contaminated sites
9	Soil and the digital agenda
10	Soil data and monitoring
11	Soil research and innovation
12	Private finance and EU funding
13	Soil literacy and societal engagement

candidate questions. These were then reviewed for redundancy and consolidated where actions overlapped substantively, resulting in the final set of 64 items that collectively cover the full scope of the Strategy’s outlined actions. Each thematic section also included one qualitative open-ended question aimed at capturing additional suggestions by the respondents (not analysed in this quantitative section).

Respondents were asked to rate the degree of a “knowledge gap” on soil topics for each relevant question on a 5-point Likert scale (Table 2); it should be noted that respondents were not required to answer all questions, but only those pertaining to their field of expertise and personal sensibilities.

No formal pilot study was conducted prior to the full survey deployment. However, the questionnaire was reviewed internally by the consortium partners for clarity and completeness before distribution. Post-hoc reliability analysis (Cronbach’s $\alpha \geq 0.70$; see Section 2.4) confirmed strong internal consistency across the 64 items, providing evidence that the instrument produced reliable measurements despite the absence of a formal piloting phase.

TABLE 2 Criteria for knowledge gap evaluation.

Score	Gap interpretation	Description
1	No gaps	Topic well addressed; planned actions sufficient
2	Minor gaps	Topic extensively treated; improvements possible for increased effectiveness
3	Moderate gaps	Topic addressed, but importance not sufficiently recognized; actions insufficient
4	Some important gaps	Topic not sufficiently addressed; implemented actions not commensurate with importance
5	Many important gaps	Topic not considered; actions almost non-existent

2.2 Stakeholder sampling and data collection

For the purpose of this work, stakeholders were experts dealing with soil health and connected items (e.g. sustainable soil management) in different sectors (e.g. agriculture, soil science, spatial planning), at different scales (e.g. national, regional, local), and in different areas of the world.

Inclusion criteria for the survey were: (a) professional engagement with soil health issues through research, policy, practice, or advocacy; (b) active involvement in soil-related activities at any institutional level; and (c) ability to complete the English-language questionnaire. Exclusion criteria: completed questionnaires that contained no rated answers within the core sections were excluded from the analysis (10 of 89 received questionnaires were removed on this basis).

To identify specific stakeholders worldwide, we pursued the following steps.

- i. we performed a web search without territorial limits on “Soil Health Initiatives and Programs” that were underway in January 2023 (start date of the “Benchmarks” project). Initially, 68 Initiatives/Programs were identified, and their responsible persons/managers were contacted by phone or email, yielding 19 questionnaires from the most motivated experts (response rate: 28%).
- ii. EU Stakeholders (public environmental agencies, private companies, multilevel policymakers/government actors, farmers associations) were contacted individually through the networks of the following projects Consortium Partners: “Benchmarks”, Landsupport, Soil4Med.
- iii. Similarly, to engage stakeholder from a global scale, soil experts from North and South America, Africa, Asia, and Oceania were contacted through the networks of the above mentioned projects.
- iv. Coordinators or persons responsible for EU research projects were also engaged if their project had the term “soil health” in the project abstract. This resulted in contact with 56 projects.

A total of 89 questionnaires were received, of which 79 were considered usable. Due to the cascading nature of dissemination through consortium partner networks (channels ii and iii), the exact total number of invitations sent cannot be precisely quantified. For the traceable channels, we contacted 68 initiative managers (channel i, 28% response rate) and 56 EU project coordinators (channel iv).

TABLE 3 Examples of type of stakeholders contacted, organised by macro-category.

Macro-category	Examples
International bodies	EUSO
National Authorities	Environment Agency Austria (EAA), Australian government
Regional Authorities	Regional agencies for environmental protection, regione campania
Private companies	Syngenta foundation for sustainable Agriculture, risorsa srl
Universities and research organizations	Cornell university, soil health institute, Qinghai normal university, commonwealth scientific and industrial research organisation (CSIRO, Australian national science agency)
Soil health initiatives and NGO	Soil initiative for Africa

We therefore characterize this as a purposive expert sample rather than a probability sample, consistent with comparable stakeholder surveys in EU soil research (Mason et al., 2023; Roca Vallejo et al., 2025). The goal of this effort was not to collect a sample large enough for population-level statistical inference, but rather to collect and explore expert opinions from informed professionals.

In all instances, when completing the questionnaire, stakeholders expressed their personal views, which do not necessarily reflect the official positions of their institutions or specific projects. Data were collected anonymously to ensure impartial responses. The estimated time to complete the questionnaire ranged from 15 to 20 min.

The sample comprises stakeholders from diverse sectors (e.g., Government, Research, NGO) and fields of expertise (e.g., Policy making, Agriculture, Soil science). In Table 3, we report some examples of the types of stakeholders engaged, providing an overview of the quality of our respondents.

Potential sources of bias are acknowledged. The purposive sampling strategy introduces self-selection bias, as only motivated experts completed the questionnaire. The Research sector is the most represented category (32.9%), while NGOs (5.1%) and certain fields of expertise (e.g., Forestry) are substantially underrepresented. These imbalances limit the generalizability of sub-group comparisons but enhance the depth of expert insight within the represented categories. The implications of these limitations are further discussed in Section 5.

2.3 Comparative evaluation of soil knowledge gap analysis

In addition to the “Benchmarks” stakeholder perception analysis, soil knowledge gap analysis had been performed by two important projects: “Soil Mission Support” (SMS) and “SOLO Think Tanks”. To contextualize and triangulate our findings, we conducted a qualitative thematic comparison aligning the three projects’ findings by common policy domains. This comparison is

qualitative rather than statistically direct, given the fundamentally different methodologies employed by each project:

SMS (Deliverable D2.4; Mason et al., 2023): A high-level literature review and stakeholder perception study. Data type: bibliometric gap frequencies from a stocktake of 15,700 articles, supplemented by stakeholder consultation (93 respondents/100 participants).

SOLO Think Tanks (various authors): Transdisciplinary, expert-led scoping studies focusing on detailed thematic actions. Data type: expert priority rankings and qualitative gap categorizations (Knowledge Development Gaps vs. Knowledge Application Gaps) produced by small teams of specialists (10–20 per theme). Relevant publications include Almás et al. (2025), Farfan et al. (2025), Frezzi et al. (2025), Hultman et al. (2025), Roca-Vallejo et al. (2025), Struyf et al. (2025), and Zoka et al. (2025).

“Benchmarks” (this study): Quantitative perception analysis using Likert-scale scores (1–5) from 79 stakeholders across 64 items mapped to the EU Soil Strategy’s 13 action areas.

The comparative findings are presented in Section 4 (Discussion) and summarized in Table 8. Additional supporting references include Maenhout et al. (2024), and Löbmann et al. (2022).

2.4 Statistical approach and data analysis

To ensure a rigorous and multidimensional assessment of stakeholder perceptions, the questionnaire data analysis employed a comprehensive statistical framework in R (version 4.5.2; R Core Team, 2024), beginning with data screening for missing values and distributional assumptions, followed by reliability analysis where Cronbach’s alpha ($\alpha \geq 0.70$; Cronbach, 1951) and supplementary indices (standardized alpha, Guttman’s lambda-6, item total correlations, and split half reliability) confirmed strong internal consistency across the 64 Likert-scale items.

Missing data handling: Of the 5,056 potential data points (79 participants \times 64 items), 1,291 values were missing (25.5% missingness), with an average of 16.3 missing values per participant and 20.2 per item. Missing data analysis using the naniar package (Tierney et al., 2021) revealed no systematic patterns, supporting the assumption that data were missing completely at random (MCAR). Given this pattern, missing data were handled via pairwise deletion (available-case analysis) for all statistical tests, maximizing the use of available information without imputation.

Evaluation of knowledge and implementation gaps relied on a dual inferential framework. Differences in perceptions across various organization types and fields of expertise were assessed using one-way ANOVA, with results cross-verified using Kruskal–Wallis non-parametric tests to control for distributional assumptions. Significant omnibus tests were followed by Tukey’s HSD post-hoc pairwise comparisons, utilizing Bonferroni corrections to rigorously control the family-wise error rate. The analysis prioritized practical significance alongside statistical significance by calculating effect sizes (Cohen’s d and η^2).

All analyses were conducted in R (version 4.5.2) using RStudio (2025.09.01 Build 401). Key packages included the tidyverse suite for data manipulation and visualization (Wickham et al., 2019), psych

for reliability (Revelle, 2024) and naniar for missing data diagnostics (Tierney et al., 2021). Supplementary visualization was facilitated by ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), likert (Bryer and Speerschnieder, 2016), and corrrplot (Wei and Simko, 2021).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Sample characteristics and data quality

The final sample ($N = 79$) comprised stakeholders representing five organization types and seven fields of expertise. Participants completed 64 Likert-scale items assessing perceptions of EU Soil Strategy initiatives. The overall response rate was 74%.

3.2 Stakeholder profile

The composition of the sample is shown in Figure 1. The most numerous respondents, catalogued by type of organization, were from Research (32.9%), followed by Government (26.6%) and Education (21.5%). The most represented fields of expertise are Soil Science (38%), Agriculture (30.4%), and Environment (12.7%). Some fields of expertise were strongly underrepresented (e.g. forestry, $n = 1$) and are therefore not discussed in subsequent disaggregated analyses.

The demographic distribution by organization type revealed substantial variation in representation. This distribution has implications for statistical power in group comparisons, particularly for detecting differences involving the NGO sector ($n = 4$). The small NGO sample size creates challenges for achieving statistical significance even when practical differences are large—a pattern observed in subsequent analyses.

3.3 Overall response patterns and the knowledge-implementation gap

The grand mean (M) across all 64 items was 3.65 ($SD = 1.18$), significantly above the neutral midpoint of 3.0, indicating that stakeholders perceive substantial room for improvement across the topics investigated. Distribution analysis (Figure 2) revealed

strong identification of knowledge gaps: 60.8% of all responses were in the high range (Some important gaps: 32.4%, Many important gaps: 28.4%), while only 17.2% were low (Minor gaps: 11.5%, No gaps: 5.7%), and 21.9% were neutral. The modal response category was “Some important gaps” (rating of 4), and the important-to-minor gaps response ratio of 3.5:1.

Distributional analysis (Figure 3; Supplementary Material, Annex VII) confirmed that responses were systematically clustered toward higher gap scores (average skewness: -0.60) with slightly platykurtic distributions (average kurtosis: -0.50), indicating genuine heterogeneity of opinion rather than artificial consensus. These distributional properties remain within commonly accepted thresholds for parametric methods, and consistency between parametric ANOVA and non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis tests in subsequent analyses confirmed that minor departures from normality did not bias inferential conclusions. Detailed distributional statistics are provided in the Supplementary Material, (Annexes II–VIII).

Figure 4 presents heatmaps of all responses by organization type and field of expertise, providing a preliminary visual overview of inter-group variation.

3.4 Sectional prioritization

The ranking of the 13 thematic sections highlights a hierarchy of perceived barriers (Table 4). The most significant deficits were identified in the biological and ecological domains. “Soil biodiversity for human, animal, and plant health” (Mean Score: 3.85), followed by “Soil for healthy water resources” (3.71) and “Making Sustainable Soil Management (SSM) the new normal” (3.71). The fact that SSM - the core operational goal of the strategy - is rated as the third-highest gap implies that the fundamental definition and practical application of “sustainability” remain elusive for many practitioners. “Private finance and EU funding” (3.70) also ranked among the top four gaps.

In contrast, “Soil and the digital agenda” was identified as the least critical area (Mean Score: 3.47), indicating that digital tools and monitoring technologies are perceived as more mature than the biological or financial frameworks required to support them. Similarly, “Preventing desertification” (3.56) and “Restoring degraded soils” (3.57) received comparatively lower gap scores.

FIGURE 2

Distribution of responses across the 5-point Likert scale (1 = No knowledge gaps to 5 = Many knowledge gaps; lower scores = fewer gaps (better)). The modal response category was “Important gaps” (4), representing 32.4% of all responses. Gaps in the range four to five comprised 60.8% of the total. Total responses = 3765.

3.5 Most critical gaps: high-intensity failure points

To provide granular insight, the specific questions with the highest and lowest mean scores were isolated (Table 5) to identify bottlenecks where current policy or science is failing most acutely. The analysis shows a mean score range of 3.30–3.98 across the 64 items. This 0.68-point difference (14% of the scale) indicates that stakeholders clearly differentiated between the complexity of various soil health topics.

The highest perceived gaps centre on ecosystem integration (Q31, Mean: 3.98) and soil biodiversity (Q15, Mean: 3.97; Q17, Mean: 3.94). These items exhibit strongly negative skewness (−0.85 to −1.01), indicating high consensus that these are critical, under-addressed areas. The highest-rated issue is not a lack of raw data, but the inability to integrate ecosystem services into political decision-making. This is reinforced by Q22 (Mean: 3.93), dealing with the sustainable use of soil and connected ecosystem services.

It is notable that in the top nine questions by average rating, “management practices” appears five times (out of ten in the entire questionnaire), followed by the words “ecosystem services,” which appear in three times. This pattern suggests that the stakeholders recognize the critical influence of management practices on soil health yet acknowledge that our knowledge of these dynamics is still evolving, as factors such as pedo-climatic context and specific management combinations create interaction effects that remain difficult to quantify.

In contrast, technical monitoring systems like LUCAS (Q50, mean: 3.30) and digital tools/Copernicus (Q45, mean: 3.39) received the lowest gap scores, with weaker negative skewness (−0.28 to −0.56), suggesting more heterogeneous opinions.

Questions with the lowest perceived knowledge gaps generally refer to specific, well-defined topics (pesticides and sludge directives, industrial emissions, peatlands). The relatively low ranking of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in the lowest-gap list, despite its

recent introduction to the discourse, may reflect growing awareness of this issue compared to more established topics.

The t-test comparing the 5 highest-rated against the 5 lowest-rated questions confirms a significant difference ($t(78) = 8.23$, $p < 0.001$), reinforcing the view that stakeholders distinguish clearly between areas of confidence and areas of perceived failure.

Table 6 presents a complementary analysis based on the frequency of maximum gap ratings (score of 5). Funding emerged as a top-four priority when measured by frequency of maximum scores, with Q55 (funding for soil biodiversity research) and Q56 (funding to address soil degradation) receiving 27 and 26 maximum-gap votes respectively. A notable divergence appears regarding Q52 (developing a soil dashboard with reliable indicators): while it ranks only 28th in average score, it received the second-highest frequency of “5” ratings, suggesting polarization driven largely by the Soil Science community, who were responsible for over a third of these maximum-gap votes.

3.6 Disaggregated analyses: differences by stakeholder type and expertise

Disaggregating responses by stakeholder type and expertise is essential for informing targeted policy interventions, as uniform gap scores may mask divergent priorities that require distinct policy instruments. The overall mean gap score of 3.65 confirms a severe systemic challenge, but a detailed disaggregation reveals meaningful perceptual differences between groups.

3.6.1 Knowledge gaps by field of expertise

Figure 5 presents a visual analysis of mean responses grouped by field of expertise. The Spatial Planning category identifies greater gaps than the other categories. This finding is of considerable importance, as it highlights that experts bearing substantial responsibility of the use of soils (e.g. soil sealing, new urban

setting) are also those emphasising the existence of many knowledge gaps.

Figure 6 compares the Agriculture and Soil Science groups (responses with a delta of average values greater than 0.5). In most cases, soil science identifies larger gaps than agriculture, possibly reflecting the specific sensitivity of soil science experts. The Soil Science category shows greater gaps in relation to excavated soils, land take, soil biodiversity, and soil monitoring. The Agriculture group highlights specific issues such as the need for a clear definition of net land take and concerns about microplastics and biodegradability. However, Agriculture ranks below other groups across the entire sections on digital agenda, data and monitoring, finance, and soil literacy.

The Environment category shows a distinctive pattern, consistently falling below average in the sections on climate change mitigation, circular economy, and soil biodiversity,

suggesting these experts consider current knowledge on these topics more adequate. Conversely, this group identifies above-average gaps in sections on SSM, restoring degraded soils, and soil research and innovation.

3.6.2 Knowledge gaps by type of organization

Figure 7 presents mean responses grouped by organization type. Discussion focuses the two groups exhibiting the most significant differences: NGOs and Research.

The Research category tends to follow the general trend, identifying greater gaps in many areas and never scoring significantly below the average of the other stakeholders. However, the NGO category assigns substantially lower values to many gaps. Some NGO scores are equal to or lower than 2, specifically regarding harmonizing soil quality considerations and

FIGURE 4 (A) Inter-rater agreement heatmap on mean gap rating by organization type. Colour scale: Blue (1–2) = Few gaps; Yellow (3) = Moderate; Red (4–5) = Many gaps. Use abbreviated Q-labels with companion key in [Supplementary Material \(Annes I\)](#). (B) Inter-rater agreement heatmap on mean gap rating by field of expertise. Same colour scale as [Figure 4A](#).

integrating a pollution module in LUCAS (average: 1.83). Instead, NGOs identify significant gaps in practical actions, such as management of organic soils (e.g., limit drainage of wetlands, restore peatlands), promoting SSM through voluntary commitments, and providing farmers with fertilizer recommendations.

The “Government” category identifies major gaps regarding funding for land degradation, soil contamination, and the development of technologies for assessing soil quality. However, it scores well below other groups on questions about a “passport for excavated soil” and farmers fertilizer recommendations, possibly reflecting the difficulty of implementing such suggestions in policies.

3.6.3 Statistical differences between groups

These sub-group findings should be interpreted as exploratory given the purposive sampling strategy and modest sample size, particularly for the NGO sub-group (n = 4). They identify hypothesis-generating patterns that warrant confirmation through larger-scale surveys. With N = 79 and five organization-type groups,

the study is adequately powered to detect large effects (Cohen’s d ≥ 0.8) but may miss smaller differences.

[Table 7](#) reports pairwise Tukey test and the standardized effect sizes (Cohen’s d Effect Size) While pairwise comparisons did not reveal statistically significant differences between organization types (all p > .05), NGO respondents showed notably lower agreement scores with large effect sizes (d = 0.98–1.14) compared to Education, Government, and Research organizations. These findings, approaching statistical significance (p = .056–.062), suggesting meaningful attitudinal differences that the current sample size may lack power to confirm statistically. This pattern reinforces the qualitative observation that NGO representatives, unlike government researchers and experts, systematically perceive fewer gaps in theoretical or systemic areas, focusing instead on acute practical obstacles to on-the-ground implementation. Consequently, this cognitive divergence highlights a fundamental disconnect in how the soil health challenge is framed—a gap that must be explicitly addressed in future multidisciplinary policy design and explored through broader research with larger sample sizes.

TABLE 4 The 13 thematic sections in order of overall average score (from highest to lowest).

Rank	Section	Mean gap score
1	Soil biodiversity for human, animal and plant health	3.85
2	Soil for healthy water resources	3.71
3	Making sustainable soil management (SSM) the new normal	3.71
4	Private finance and EU funding	3.70
5	Soil for climate change mitigation and Adaptation	3.67
6	Soil data and monitoring	3.64
7	Soil literacy and societal engagement	3.63
8	Soil research and innovation	3.63
9	Soil and the circular economy	3.61
10	Preventing soil pollution	3.61
11	Restoring degraded soils and remediating contaminated sites	3.57
12	Preventing desertification	3.56
13	Soil and the digital agenda	3.47

TABLE 5 Most and least important knowledge Gaps (Ranked by mean score; standard deviation is reported in parentheses). Top 9 and bottom 9 questions shown; complete table available in [Supplementary Material](#).

Rank	Q No.	Question	Mean	SD
1	Q31	Integrating ecosystems and their services into decision-making	3.98	(1.02)
2	Q15	Building knowledge on soil biodiversity and AMR genes in agricultural soils under different management regimes	3.97	(1.01)
3	Q17	Striving for a global biodiversity framework recognizing soil biodiversity importance	3.94	(0.99)
4	Q22	Assessing requirements for sustainable soil use to maintain ecosystem services	3.93	(0.97)
5	Q8	Setting ambitious national/regional/local targets to reduce net land take by 2030	3.90	(1.13)
6	Q18	Mapping, assessing, protecting and restoring soil biodiversity	3.88	(1.07)
7	Q20	Facilitating exchange of practices on the soil-water-sediment nexus	3.87	(1.10)
8	Q23	Defining a set of SSM practices adapted to soil ecosystem variability	3.85	(1.17)
9	Q4	Promoting investments in projects that sustainably manage soils	3.85	(1.07)
...
56	Q46	Providing farmers recommendations about fertiliser use	3.42	(1.23)
57	Q54	Implementing ambitious roadmaps for research and innovation	3.42	(1.09)
58	Q36	Revising the directive on sustainable use of pesticides/Sewage sludge directive	3.41	(1.11)
59	Q34	Publishing information on land degradation and desertification in the EU	3.40	(1.28)
60	Q30	Proposing a legislative framework for an EU sustainable food system	3.39	(1.23)
61	Q45	Enhancing use of digital tools, copernicus, and LISE	3.39	(1.16)
62	Q43	Revising the industrial emissions directive/Environmental liability directive	3.37	(1.31)
63	Q2	Assessing the state of peatlands	3.32	(1.11)
64	Q50	Integrating a pollution module in the LUCAS soil programme	3.30	(1.17)

TABLE 6 Most critical gaps (Ranked by frequency of high scores). The first 12 rows contain information on the questions that received the highest number of 5-scores. The following 10 rows contain information on the questions with the lowest. Complete table in [Supplementary Material](#).

Rank	Q No.	Question	Count (5)
1	Q55	Providing substantial funding to research solutions to increase soil biodiversity	27
2	Q23	Defining a set of SSM practices adapted to soil ecosystem variability	26
3	Q52	Developing a soil dashboard with a set of reliable soil indicators	26
4	Q56	Providing substantial funding to address soil degradation	26
5	Q15	Building knowledge on soil biodiversity and AMR in agricultural soils	24
6	Q24	Providing assistance to member states for 'test your soil for free'	24
7	Q48	Assessing impact and monitoring soil and soil biodiversity	24
8	Q19	Addressing integration and coordination of soil and water management	23
9	Q31	Integrating ecosystems and their services into decision-making	23
10	Q8	Setting ambitious targets to reduce net land take by 2030	22
11	Q18	Mapping, assessing, protecting and restoring soil biodiversity	22
12	Q57	Providing funding to pilot innovative decontamination technologies	22
...
55	Q6	Investigation of excavated soil streams in the EU	11
56	Q30	Proposing a legislative framework for EU sustainable food system	11
57	Q42	Developing an EU priority list for contaminants of concern	11
58	Q45	Enhancing use of digital tools, copernicus, and LISE	11
59	Q63	Integrating soil degradation in EU sustainability competence framework	11
60	Q16	Assessing alien flatworm species risk for invasive species list	10
61	Q1	Management of organic soils (e.g., limit drainage, restore peatlands)	9
62	Q36	Revising pesticides directive/Sewage sludge directive	8
63	Q50	Integrating a pollution module in the LUCAS soil programme	8
64	Q2	Assessing the state of peatlands	6

4 Discussion

4.1 The Governance-Science Gap

The results reveal a consistent pattern that we term the “Governance-Science Gap”: stakeholders perceive that the primary barriers to soil health lie not in technical or monitoring deficiencies but in the failure to translate existing scientific knowledge into governance and decision-making. The highest-rated gap (Q31: integrating ecosystems and their services into decision-making, Mean: 3.98) directly concerns the science-policy interface, while the lowest-rated items concern established monitoring tools (LUCAS, Copernicus). This contrast suggests that stakeholders trust the available metrics but lack the mechanisms to apply this data effectively to policy and management.

This finding aligns with the broader sustainability science literature on “knowledge-action gaps,” where the accumulation of scientific data does not automatically lead to improved environmental outcomes (Löbmann et al., 2022). Our

quantitative evidence provides a specific, soil-focused dimension to this general phenomenon. The systematic shift in skewness—from approximately -0.90 for aspirational policy goals to -0.30 for specific implementation actions—quantifies this gap: uncertainty decreases as policy proposals move from conceptual objectives toward specific regulatory and monitoring actions, suggesting that while the “what” (policy objectives) is clear, the “how” (operationalization) remains subject to diverse institutional interpretations.

4.2 The management practice nexus

The prominence of “management practices” in the top-rated gaps (five of the top nine questions) reflects a recognized but unresolved challenge. Stakeholders acknowledge the critical influence of management practices on soil health but recognize that site-specific guidance remains elusive. This is consistent with [Terribile et al. \(2024\)](#), who demonstrated that sustainable soil management is a “wicked problem” where factors such as pedo-

FIGURE 5 Mean Response by Field of Expertise. Error bars = 95% CI; Dashed line: Moderate (3); Dotted line: Grand mean.

FIGURE 6 Comparison between the "Agriculture" and "Soil Science" groups: responses with a delta of average values greater than 0.5.

climatic context and specific management combinations create interaction effects that are difficult to quantify. Similarly, Maenhout et al. (2024) found that while soil organic carbon sequestration is widely studied, knowledge of critical trade-offs with non-CO₂ greenhouse gases and nitrate leaching remains limited. The "gap" identified by our stakeholders is therefore not a lack of fundamental data but a lack of site-specific, integrated management advice that accounts for synergies and trade-offs.

4.3 Divergent Stakeholder Priorities

The disaggregated analyses reveal a notable perceptual disconnect between groups that has direct implications for R&I agenda design. The NGO category consistently assigns lower gap scores to theoretical and systemic areas while emphasizing acute practical obstacles such as funding and the management of organic soils. In contrast, the Research category

TABLE 7 Pairwise comparisons of perceived knowledge gap scores by organization type: Mean differences, 95% confidence intervals, adjusted p-values, and standardized effect sizes.

Comparison	M(G1)	M(G2)	ΔM	95% CI	p(adj)	d	Effect
Educ. vs. Gov	3.83	3.68	0.149	[-0.54, 0.84]	0.974	0.236	Small
Educ. vs. NGO	3.83	2.94	0.891	[-0.01, 1.80]	0.056	1.141	Large
Educ. vs. Other	3.83	3.75	0.075	[-0.87, 1.02]	0.999	0.087	Negl
Educ. vs. Research	3.83	3.77	0.063	[-0.60, 0.72]	0.999	0.099	Negl
Gov. vs. NGO	3.68	2.94	0.742	[-0.14, 1.62]	0.137	0.976	Large
Gov. vs. Other	3.68	3.75	-0.074	[-1.00, 0.85]	0.999	-0.088	Negl
Gov. vs. Research	3.68	3.77	-0.086	[-0.71, 0.53]	0.995	-0.137	Negl
NGO vs. Other	2.94	3.75	-0.816	[-1.91, 0.28]	0.237	-0.697	Medium
NGO vs. Research	2.94	3.77	-0.828	[-1.68, 0.03]	0.062	-1.114	Large
Other vs. Research	3.75	3.77	-0.013	[-0.91, 0.89]	1.000	-0.016	Negl

M = Mean. ΔM , Mean Difference; CI, Confidence Interval. P-values adjusted using Bonferroni method. Cohen’s d thresholds: Negligible ($|d| < 0.2$), Small ($0.2 \leq |d| < 0.5$), Medium ($0.5 \leq |d| < 0.8$), Large ($|d| \geq 0.8$). Positive mean differences indicate Group 1 perceived larger gaps than Group 2.

identifies greater gaps in fundamental knowledge areas. The large effect sizes ($d = 0.98\text{--}1.14$) for NGO comparisons, despite non-significant p-values, indicate a substantive cognitive divergence that is coherent with the wicked nature of sustainable soil management and it must be explicitly addressed in future multi-stakeholder policy design processes.

The finding that Spatial Planning experts identify the largest gaps overall is particularly policy-relevant, as these professionals bear direct responsibility for land-use decisions that affect soil sealing and urban development. This finding highlights the urgent need to provide appropriate data and decision-support tools to spatial planners—a group not traditionally central to soil health discourse.

4.4 Comparative analysis with other EU projects

To contextualize these findings, we compare our results with those of two complementary EU projects—Soil Mission Support (SMS) and SOLO—that have also assessed soil knowledge gaps, albeit using fundamentally different methodologies. Table 8 provides a structured comparison. Three convergent themes emerge from this triangulation:

Abundance of data, scarcity of context. SMS confirms a high volume of research on “Assessment & Modelling” and “Basic knowledge production” but reveals that operational domains

TABLE 8 Comparative summary of three EU soil knowledge gap assessments.

Dimension	SMS (Mason et al., 2023)	SOLO think tanks (various, 2025)	Benchmarks (this study)
Methodology	Bibliometric stocktake (15,700 articles in scopus) + stakeholder consultation (93 respondents/100 participants)	Transdisciplinary expert-led scoping via 9 think tanks (10–20 specialists per theme) + stakeholder voting	Quantitative perception survey: 79 stakeholders, 64 likert-scale items mapped to 13 EU soil strategy action areas
Data type	Publication gap frequencies; consultation themes	Expert priority rankings; qualitative gap categorizations (KDG vs. KAG)	Numerical gap intensity scores (1–5 likert scale)
Governance/Policy integration	Science-based policy support is under-researched vs. Assessment & modelling	Knowledge application gaps dominate across themes; “triple H” framework identifies neglect of attitudes and behaviours	Highest gap: integrating ecosystem services into decision-making (mean: 3.98); lowest: LUCAS/Copernicus (3.30)
SSM/Management	Implementation science lagging behind basic knowledge production	Trade-offs between SOC, N ₂ O, and leaching poorly quantified; site-specific guidance lacking	SSM ranked 3rd highest gap (mean: 3.71); “management practices” appear in 5 of top 9 questions
Biodiversity/Biology	Identified as gap area in literature	Soil biodiversity conservation identified as KDG; AMR in soils emerging	Soil biodiversity section ranked highest overall (mean: 3.85); AMR question ranked 2nd by mean score
Soil literacy/Education	Awareness identified as under-researched	“Soil stewardship paradox”: High knowledge ≠ stewardship; ESD integration = KAG	Soil literacy in top third of gap scores; polarization between soil science and Agriculture groups
Digital tools/Monitoring	Assessment & modelling dominant in literature	Not a primary focus of think tanks	Lowest gap scores (digital agenda: 3.47); stakeholders trust tools but not translation to decisions
Funding	Not a primary dimension	Not explicitly quantified	Top 4 priority when measured by frequency of maximum (5) scores; Q55, Q56 received 27 and 26 votes
Key limitation	Excludes grey literature; may miss practical knowledge outside academia	Expert consensus introduces subjectivity; small team sizes	Purposive sampling; self-selection bias; small NGO sub-sample; 25.5% missingness
Unique contribution	Macro-level bibliometric baseline of research landscape	Conceptual framework (KDG vs. KAG) + “triple H” model for soil literacy	Granular, question-level stakeholder frustration data; identifies specific bottlenecks and polarization

KDG, knowledge development gap; KAG, knowledge application gap; SSM, sustainable soil management; AMR, antimicrobial resistance; SOC, soil organic carbon; ESD, education for sustainable development.

such as “Living Labs,” “Awareness,” and “Science-based policy support” are statistically under-researched (Mason et al., 2023). This bibliometric finding is corroborated by our “Benchmarks” data, where stakeholders rated “integrating ecosystems and their services into decision-making” as the single most critical gap (Mean: 3.98). Together, these independent data streams indicate a failure to translate abundant data into political decision-support tools.

The dominance of application gaps. SOLO’s methodology distinguishes between Knowledge Development Gaps (KDG)—where new scientific understanding is required—and Knowledge Application Gaps (KAG)—where the barrier is translating existing knowledge into practice (Roca Vallejo et al., 2025). The finding that soil biology and soil literacy are high-gap areas in the “Benchmarks” survey aligns with SOLO’s identification of application gaps in these same domains. For instance, Roca Vallejo et al. (2025) categorize the lack of frameworks to integrate soil into Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) as a Knowledge Application Gap—a finding directly parallel to the high “Benchmarks” scores for soil literacy

questions. SOLO’s “Triple H” framework (Head, Heart, Hands) explains why high levels of scientific output do not correlate with stewardship: knowledge without “care” leads to what they term the “soil stewardship paradox.”

The complexity barrier. The frustration expressed by “Benchmarks” stakeholders regarding SSM (Rank 3) is not a result of ignorance but of scientific complexity. Maenhout et al. (2024) showed that the interaction effects between tillage, fertilization, and water management are complex and poorly quantified for diverse pedoclimatic contexts. Thus, the convergent message from all three projects is that the primary barrier is not a scarcity of fundamental science but a failure of translation—a “Technical-Institutional Mismatch.”

The distinct contribution of the “Benchmarks” study within this landscape is its granularity. While SMS provides a macro-level bibliometric baseline and SOLO offers expert consensus on thematic priorities, “Benchmarks” provides numerically scored, question-level perception data directly mapped to the EU Soil

Strategy's 13 action areas. This allows identification of specific bottlenecks (e.g., the polarization around Q52, soil dashboard indicators) that broader approaches cannot detect.

5 Limitations and scope

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting these findings. Regarding the sample: the purposive (non-probability) sampling strategy introduces self-selection bias, as only motivated experts completed the survey. The Research sector is overrepresented (32.9%), while NGOs ($n = 4$) and certain expertise fields (Forestry, $n = 1$) are substantially underrepresented, limiting the statistical power and generalizability of sub-group comparisons. The English-language requirement may have excluded relevant non-Anglophone experts.

Regarding the instrument: no formal pilot study was conducted prior to deployment, although post-hoc reliability analysis (Cronbach's $\alpha \geq 0.70$) confirmed internal consistency. Respondents were not required to answer all questions, resulting in 25.5% missingness; while missing data diagnostics suggest MCAR patterns, this rate introduces uncertainty in item-level estimates. The 5-point Likert scale, while widely used, may lack sensitivity for capturing nuanced differences between closely rated items.

Regarding the comparative analysis: SMS, SOLO, and "Benchmarks" employed fundamentally different methodologies, making direct quantitative comparison impossible. SMS excluded grey literature, which may cause it to underestimate practical knowledge that exists outside academia. The thematic alignment across projects is interpretive rather than statistically tested.

Regarding generalizability: these findings reflect the perceptions of a specific expert community, primarily EU-based researchers and government officials, and should not be extrapolated to all soil stakeholders globally. The results are exploratory and hypothesis-generating; they identify patterns and priorities that warrant confirmation through larger-scale, probability-based surveys.

6 Conclusion

The assessment of stakeholder perceptions presented in this study offers a granular view of the barriers impeding the transition to healthy soils in Europe.

By triangulating our quantitative survey results with bibliometric baselines (Soil Mission Support) and expert consensus (SOLO), we arrive at three critical conclusions:

The Governance-Science Gap. The survey results indicate a stark contrast between technical capability and operational governance. Stakeholders ranked the integration of ecosystem services into decision-making as the most severe gap. Conversely, established technical monitoring tools (e.g., LUCAS, Copernicus) received the lowest gap scores, suggesting that stakeholders trust the available metrics but lack the mechanisms to apply this data effectively to policy and management.

Divergent Stakeholder Priorities. There is a notable perceptual disconnect between groups. While the research community continues to identify gaps in fundamental knowledge regarding climate and biodiversity, NGOs and practitioners emphasize the lack

of practical implementation support, specifically regarding funding and the management of organic soils. This disconnect highlights a fundamental challenge in framing multi-stakeholder R&I agendas. **The Technical-Institutional Mismatch.** The primary obstacle to achieving the EU soil policy targets appears to be not a scarcity of fundamental science, but a failure of translation. Our analysis confirms the existence of widespread Knowledge Gaps in operational support systems—a failure to translate existing data into site-specific, integrated management advice that accounts for complex trade-offs.

Based on these findings, we propose the following actionable policy recommendations:

First, future soil-focused research project (e.g. Horizon Europe soil missions and other R&I programming) should allocate a dedicated funding stream for governance-integration research—specifically, the development of tools and approaches that translate monitoring data into decision-support instruments for policymakers and land managers—rather than focusing primarily on additional biophysical data collection.

Second, soil health initiative (e.g. EU Soil Observatory and similar initiatives worldwide) should establish structured multi-stakeholder dialogues that explicitly bring together NGOs (who prioritize practical support and funding) and researchers (who focus on theoretical gaps) to co-design R&I priorities aligned with on-the-ground implementation needs. The significant perceptual divergence documented here suggests that current agenda-setting processes may not adequately represent all stakeholder perspectives.

Third, States (e.g. EU member states) should pilot soil health literacy programs that integrate the attitudinal ("Heart") and behavioural ("Hands") dimensions identified through the SOLO framework, moving beyond purely cognitive ("Head") approaches to soil education. Our data confirm that soil literacy and societal engagement remain high-gap areas that traditional knowledge-transfer models have not resolved.

Addressing this Technical-Institutional Mismatch—by evolving from the exclusive accumulation of biophysical parameters to investment in governance structures, economic incentives, and educational frameworks—is the prerequisite for realizing the functional recovery of soil systems in Europe and worldwide.

Data availability statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/[Supplementary Material](#), further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Ethics statement

Ethical approval was not required for the studies involving humans. The studies were conducted in accordance with the local legislation and institutional requirements. Written informed consent for participation was not required from the participants or the participants' legal guardians/next of kin in accordance with the national legislation and institutional requirements.

Author contributions

GF: Data curation, Investigation, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing. MHS: Formal Analysis, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing. CVM: Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing. FT: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing.

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Conflict of interest

The author(s) declared that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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